

FORMING OF NONCRIMP FABRIC COMPOSITES WITH EMBEDDED CABLING

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1 Introduction

Government regulations push automotive manufacturers to continually increase fuel efficiency **Error! Reference source not found.** As a result, automotive companies are exploring lightweight materials as alternatives to aluminum and steel. Of special interest for decreasing vehicular weight is the use of fiber-reinforced composites. Both woven fabric and non-crimp fabrics (NCFs) have been under investigation for this purpose [2][3]. These materials are attractive due to their high strength-to-weight ratios and corrosion resistance compared to traditional metal parts. An additional benefit of these materials relative to metals is the option to tailor their energy absorption characteristics.

NCFs are displacing woven fabrics as a preferred choice for reinforcement due to their ability to conform to complex geometries better than woven fabrics [4][5]. Another advantage of NCFs compared to woven fabrics is the absence of undulations (crimp) which enhances in-plane mechanical properties. These undulations reduce the efficiency of the straight-line load path as compared to what can be realized in an NCF. The main mode of deformation for an NCF during forming is shearing as the absence of crimp limits the extensibility of the yarns. Unlike woven fabrics, where the weave pattern holds the yarns together, in NCFs thin stitching is often used to hold the yarns in position relative to one another. In addition, the stitching improves the handling stability and delamination toughness of the fabric. NCFs can be either a dry fabric or a pre-preg. Pre-preg NCFs are an attractive option for high-throughput thermoforming processes because the pre-preg removes the need for a resin infusion step, and the pre-preg may also act as a means to hold the yarns in position thereby eliminating the need for the stitches and the cost associated with the stitching process. However, the thermostamping of unstitched fabrics can present challenges as the resin viscosity

decreases during forming due to the high temperature of the tool. This decrease in viscosity allows the yarns to move freely relative to each other, which can cause undesirable defects such as out-of-plane wrinkles and yarn spreading or bunching. Thus, the fabric type and architecture, as well as its drapeability and permeability when the process requires a resin-infusion step, must be carefully considered as the formability, quality and performance of the final part are highly dependent on those characteristics.

Modeling the forming of fiber-reinforced composites has been of interest for more than a decade [2-12]. Uncertainties in both material behavior and processing conditions often result in overdesigned parts that unnecessarily increase weight and costs. Having a design tool that can simulate the manufacturing process and reduce or remove the need for the iterative design-build-test process would decrease the design cycle time and cost. However, the design tool must be able to capture the evolution of the orientation of the yarns during forming and predict whether or not defects will develop during forming. Fig. 1 shows a schematic of common defects, such as out-of-plane waves or wrinkles, folding, in-plane waviness and tearing. These defects compromise the quality of the formed part and reduce strength and fatigue performance. Thus, the design tool must also be capable of capturing where such defects may develop during the composite manufacturing process. It is also important for the tool to predict and simulate the orientation and density of the fibers as these features affect the permeability of the fabric which is important for infusion and molding processes. This tool could be used as a design-aid to determine acceptable processing conditions such as mold geometry, punch velocity, binder pressure, and the initial ply orientations to ensure a part can be formed free of defects.

As vehicles progress to become 'smarter', the demands on the communication networks within a

vehicle will increase. Fiber-optic networks can provide the foundation for high-speed and high-bandwidth communications within a vehicle. A large-scale composite structure can incorporate interlaminar fiber-optic cabling just like a printed circuit board. Using a forming process to manufacture composite structures with embedded fiber-optic cabling can provide significant cost savings by minimizing manually-installed wiring harnesses. In addition to weight savings without having to compromise part strength, the composite layers would add protection to the fiber-optic cables. While the fiber within currently available fiber-optic cables is small, the protective coating of the cable is of a fairly significant diameter relative to the fabric thickness. This significant diameter can present challenges during forming as it can potentially lead to the formation of defects. The simulation tool would be very useful in exploring the potential challenges to integrate communication cabling into composite parts and to allow for exploring ways of reducing the adverse effects due to the presence of the embedded cabling.

Thus, the motivation for this research is to investigate the feasibility of a high-volume low-cost manufacturing process for expanding the use of composites to reduce vehicle weight and embed fiber-optic cabling for high-speed communications within a vehicle. To this end, a hybrid finite-element discrete-mesoscopic approach is proposed to model the forming of composite parts using a unidirectional glass pre-preg NCF. The forming of a hemisphere is simulated using a finite element model of the fabric, and the results are compared to a thermostamped part as a demonstration of the capabilities of the proposed methodology. Forming simulations of a NCF into a double-dome structure with geometry previously used in an international benchmarking program [6], are then performed with the validated finite element model of the fabric to explore the ability of the layered NCF to accommodate the presence of interlaminar cabling. As stated, the intent of the cabling is for use as a communication network and is analogous to a printed circuit board.

2 Background

The primary composite layup considered in this research is four layers of unidirectional fabric with a $0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ stacking sequence. The simulation approach for the modeling of two mutually perpendicular layers of fabric incorporates beam

elements to represent the tensile properties of respective yarns of each layer of the NCF and shell elements to represent the shear properties of those two layers of the NCF. Thus, Fig. 2 shows a unit cell of such a modeling approach for the case of a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ layup of two layers of the unidirectional fabric. Prior work has shown that the unit cell can be scaled such that a beam element can represent more than one yarn in the fabric without significantly impacting the fidelity of the results while reducing the computational time needed for a forming simulation. In this research, each beam element represents 10 yarns. Also, this unit cell is the same unit cell used for a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ woven fabric for which this modeling procedure has been previously documented [2]. The difference between finite element models for the two different types of fabrics is within the user subroutines which are based on characterization experiments for the specific material. Application of this procedure for a single layer of unidirectional material is discussed in [3] and [6]. It has also been previously noted that the displacement results are the same whether one layer is formed at a time or all layers are formed at the same time. Thus, stacking sequence is not important in forming even though, stacking sequence can be important in the response of the formed part to applied loads or service conditions.

This proposed method for simulating the forming of NCFs into a composite structure allows for an automated process for capturing the evolution and final configurations of the primary load carrying paths of the composite structure as defined by the yarns. The formation of defects such as those shown in Fig. 1 that may occur during the forming process can be observed in this forming simulation. This defect information can be used to guide changes in the design of the part or in the manufacturing process to minimize the potential occurrence of such defects.

3 Experimental program

The experimental program was conducted in two phases. First, material characterization tests were conducted to provide input into the simulations. Then, hemisphere forming experiments were conducted for comparison to simulation results and to explore the formability of the pre-preg NCF material.

3.1 Material characterization

Material characterization tests were completed to determine the mechanical behavior of the NCF in tension and in shear. Tensile tests were completed to characterize the tensile stiffness of the fibers, the main direction through which the load is carried during forming. Shear-frame tests were conducted to characterize the in-plane shear stiffness as shearing is the main mode of large deformation during forming. Additionally, friction tests were conducted to characterize the friction between the tool and the fabric and the friction between fabric layers.

3.1.1 Tensile characterization

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on an INSTRON 4464 universal testing machine with a 2-kN load cell. Pneumatic grips were used to clamp the samples, which were tested at a rate of 5 mm/s. Individual yarns could not be pulled out of the fabric material for testing, therefore 12.7-mm wide samples were used. A gauge length of approximately 0.5 m was chosen to minimize the effect of the deformation in the grips. To prevent slippage of the tensile specimens in the grips, the ends of the samples were embedded into Twintex® material and consolidated at 175°C.

Samples were tested at room temperature only. It was assumed that the low modulus of the uncured resin would have an insignificant effect on the tensile properties of the uncured fabric. The average tensile stiffness was determined from the slope of the load/true-strain curve and the modulus of the fibers was determined from the slope of the stress/true-strain curve (Table 1). The stress was calculated using the effective cross section of the specimen, A_{eff} , given by,

$$A_{eff} = \frac{\rho_{linear}}{VF_{glass} \cdot \rho_{glass} + (1 - VF_{glass}) \cdot \rho_{resin}} \quad (1)$$

where VF_{glass} is the glass volume fraction, ρ_{linear} is the fabric linear density, and ρ_{glass} and ρ_{resin} are the glass and resin densities, respectively [8]. Five samples were used to calculate the average values of the tensile stiffness and the modulus.

The experimental tensile modulus (24.9 ± 0.3 GPa) reported in Table 1 was compared to the analytical value (29.5 GPa) calculated from the manufacturer's reported fiber volume fraction and the tensile modulus of fiberglass. The small difference (15.6%) is attributed to material imperfections resulting from

the manufacturing process. The reasonably good agreement between the experimental and analytical moduli supports the credibility of the experimental methodology used to determine the effective tensile modulus of the yarns.

The tensile modulus of the yarns was implemented into the finite element model for forming simulations via user-defined material subroutines. The user-defined material subroutines available with Abaqus/Explicit are named VUMAT and allow for a user-supplied constitutive model to be linked with the Abaqus solver. The solver provides the state of strain to the user-defined material subroutine, and the subroutine returns the associated stress values to the solver.

3.1.2 Shear characterization

Shear-frame tests were conducted on an INSTRON 4464 universal testing machine to characterize the in-plane shear stiffness of the NCF at the handling temperature (i.e. room temperature) and the forming temperature of 50°C [3]. Fig. 3 shows the NCF mounted in the shear frame before and after deformation. Fig. 4 shows a schematic representation of the shear behavior at the handling temperature (load vs. shear angle) for the NCF during the shear test. When the test sample is mounted in the frame, the unidirectional fibers are initially parallel to each other and essentially uniformly spaced across the width of the fabric. As the frame starts to deform, the fibers begin to shear and to slip relative to one another. However, until the locking angle is reached, the yarns remain essentially parallel, although rotated from their original configuration. As the fibers rotate, they also begin to move closer to each other. The friction and compaction between the fibers causes the shear stiffness of the unidirectional pre-preg material to increase until the locking angle is reached. At the locking angle, the fibers reach a compaction limit and are no longer able to move in-plane relative to each other. They are forced to deform out of plane, which results in a decrease in the shear stiffness past the angle indicated by a dotted line in Fig. 4. The locking angle for this material at the handling and the forming temperatures is approximately 20° of shear [3].

In initial tests, an out-of-plane wave pattern was observed across the width of the test sample, and the wave extended along the entire length of the fabric. It was determined that the out-of-plane deformations were caused by the clamped fabric edges, which did

not allow individual fibers to slide relative to each other. There was concern that this edge effect could compromise the quality of the shear characterization of the fabric. Thus, the geometry of the shear-frame specimen was modified to minimize the edge effects noticed during this initial test. As shown in Fig. 5, slits were cut at every 3 mm to form the arms of the specimen in an effort to allow for in-plane sliding of the yarns in the middle of the sample. Two 5-mm strips of the same pre-preg material were taped on the outside of the region of interest to prevent fabric tearing due to the slits (Fig. 5). The length of the frame L_F was 216 mm, and the length of the fabric L_f was 130 mm. The specimen was sheared at a rate of 2 mm/s. The motivation for making the slits was based on previous shear-frame testing of woven fabrics where it was realized that by removing the cross yarns in the arms of the test specimen, the fabric would exhibit more uniform shear deformation across the sample than it would with the cross yarns [9][10].

The results for the shear behavior of the NCF at the processing temperature were compared to room-temperature results. As expected, the shear stiffness is considerably lower at the processing temperature, a phenomenon that can be attributed to the lower viscosity of the resin at the processing temperature compared to the viscosity at room temperature (Fig. 6). With a lower-viscosity resin, the tows are able to rotate more easily than with a higher-viscosity resin and thereby may have improved drapeability during a thermostamping process prior to curing [3]. Although drapeability is improved, there is a trade-off with using a lower-viscosity resin compared to a higher-viscosity resin. A lower-viscosity resin can allow defects to form more easily than a higher-viscosity resin.

The load versus shear-angle results obtained directly from the shear-frame tests were converted to shear stress versus logarithmic strain values per the methodology described in [10]. A 5th-order polynomial was fit to the resulting curve and differentiated once as described in [2] to obtain the tangent shear modulus, $G(\gamma_L)$, as a 4th-order function of the shear angle,

$$G(\gamma_L) = 16.7|\gamma_L|^4 - 33.6|\gamma_L|^3 + 23.2|\gamma_L|^2 - 5.9|\gamma_L| + 0.433 \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2 was implemented into the finite element model for forming simulations via user-defined material subroutines.

3.1.3 Friction characterization

The procedure for experimentally characterizing the friction behavior between the fabric and the tool as well as between fabric layers is discussed in detail in [6]. Based on the results documented in [6], static and dynamic coefficients of friction with exponential decay constants were incorporated into the finite element models of the hemisphere and the double-dome.

3.2 Forming experiments

Hemisphere forming experiments were completed to explore the formability of the unidirectional pre-preg NCF material and for comparison to the simulation results. An environmental chamber was used for the forming of four layers of the fabric—with a stacking sequence of $0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ at the processing temperature of 50°C . Defects such as fiber bunching and separation were observed in the regions where the fibers were oriented normal to the tool edges as shown in Fig. 7(a). The close-up view in Fig. 7(a) shows the fiber bunching and separation in detail.

4 Finite Element Modeling

Finite element models of a hemisphere were completed to investigate the capability of the beam-shell methodology and the material properties determined from the characterization experiments to capture the response of the material during a forming process. These models were completed using Abaqus/Explicit. However, this process is not limited to Abaqus/Explicit. In theory, this process for creating the design tool can be applied to any finite element software package that allows user-defined material models. For example, the methodology has been implemented into LS-DYNA [2][11]. The results from the Abaqus/Explicit finite element simulation depicted in Fig. 7(b) show excellent correlation with the actual forming experiment of Fig. 7(a). The phenomenon of the spreading and bunching of the yarns comprising the unidirectional plies observed in the forming experiment are well captured by the model.

Additionally, forming simulations of a double-dome structure with the presence of a hypothetical interlaminar cable were performed to explore the capabilities of the finite element model to accommodate the presence of cabling embedded between four layers of the unidirectional pre-preg NCF with a $0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ stacking orientation (Fig. 8). To account for four layers of the fabric,

two layers of the unit cell depicted in Fig. 2 were used in the finite element model. Each unit cell represents two layers of the NCF fabric under investigation – one layer in the 0° orientation and one layer in the 90° orientation. The cable was placed between the unit-cell layers in the finite element model, i.e. two plies on either side of the cable.

At this time, it should be noted that the fiber-optic cables currently available for vehicle applications have a protective jacketing of significantly larger diameter (~3 mm) than the optic fiber alone. However, the protective jacketing is not suitable for the high temperature (150°C) needed to cure the prepreg NCFs after forming. Note that this curing temperature is significantly higher than the processing temperature (50°C). Thus, it is the curing temperature, not the forming temperature, which limits the automated incorporation of the fiber-optic cable into the composite structure in the manner described. As a result, only a hypothetical representation of the cable that could potentially be used in future applications was modeled. The finite element simulation of the forming of the composite structure with the embedded cable has the advantage of not explicitly considering temperature. Thus, the potential for incorporating such a cable can be investigated before a suitable cable actually exists. Upon availability of a suitable cable, the material properties of the cable at the processing temperature can be considered explicitly in the model.

For the double-dome structure, the model shows that the presence of the hypothetical cable may introduce out-of-plane wave defects that could compromise part quality (Figs. 1(a) and 9). These wave defects are at least partially a result of the significant difference in the thickness between the fabric and the cable encased in a protective coating. The diameter of the protective coating of the hypothetical cable is approximately 3 mm, while the thickness of a single layer of fabric is approximately 0.2 mm. Thus, there is a ratio of 15:1 between the coating and the fiber optic. The relatively large diameter of the encased cable compared to the thickness of the fabric creates a potential for introducing defects in the formed parts. The model was used to further explore changes in the manufacturing process to potentially avoid the formation of such (or similar) defects.

For example, it should be noted that the tooling in this finite element model is slightly different from

the actual tooling in the international benchmark project. With the introduction of the cable, it was necessary to split the binder just wide enough for the cable to pass through the binder region of the tooling thereby allowing the fabric to wrap around the cable while the binder could otherwise place uniform pressure on the fabric during the forming process and avoid gap defects (Fig. 8). Also, the finite element model does not account for compaction of the cable under high curing pressure or ripping due to high tensile loads. However, a failure criterion for the breaking of yarns such that tearing can be captured by the model could be implemented if deemed necessary. In the absence of a tearing criterion in the model, the tensile stresses in the yarns can be viewed. If any tensile stresses exceed the ultimate stress of the yarn, the user can assume that tearing would have occurred.

After updating the binder so that uniform pressure could be applied to the fabric stack, it was noted that a pocket defect (Fig. 1(a)) was present on the inside of the binders (Fig. 9). Thus, it was also necessary to modify the punch geometry to accommodate the shape of the cable to allow application of uniform pressure to the fabric when the punch and die were fully closed.

At this stage, it was noted that the mesh density currently used in the model was not appropriate for the fabric stack to conform to the shape of the cable (Fig. 9) based on the tent (triangular) shape of the shell elements in the vicinity of the cable. Increasing the mesh density of the whole fabric blank is not an efficient modeling approach due to the resulting increased computational time. The only real need for increased mesh refinement is for improving the resolution around the small section of the fabric stack in the immediate area of the cable. Thus, increasing the mesh density of the elements only around the area of the cable is the preferred method as shown in Figs. 10 and 11. With this increase in mesh density, beam properties were also scaled appropriately. Note that Fig. 10 shows the deformation results from the cross-sectional view and Fig. 11 shows the deformation results from the side view. The increased mesh resolution in the region of the cable allowed the fabric to conform tightly to the shape of the cable. This method would continue to be applicable if the cable was not parallel to the edges of the shell elements. However, in that case, a larger region of refinement, and potentially a greater level of refinement, would be required for the fabric stack to conform to the cable

compared to the case when the cable is parallel to the edge of the shell elements.

These three modifications to the tooling in the finite element simulation are excellent examples of the potential of the proposed modeling as a design tool. Additional changes to the tooling, the number of fabric layers and the respective orientations of those layers could be explored to form parts free of defects while achieving good overall quality.

5 Conclusions

A discrete mesoscopic modeling approach was used for the forming of unidirectional pre-preg non-crimp fabric. Tensile tests and shear-frame tests were performed to characterize the mechanical behavior of the material and to obtain experimental data to be used in the forming simulations. These forming simulations show promise for the continued development of a predictive design tool for thermoforming structures of good quality using NCFs. Additionally, forming methodologies for incorporation of fiber-optic cables into NCF composites during an actual thermoforming step have been investigated. The procedure and modifications to the current thermostamping process as outlined in this paper show promise pending the design of a cable that can withstand the elevated processing temperatures for the NCF.

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Table 1. Tensile properties for a single ply of unidirectional prepreg NCF (\pm one standard deviation)

Modulus (GPa)	Strength (kN)
24.9 \pm 0.3	63.9 \pm 3.8

Fig. 1. Fabric defects that may occur during the forming process (a) out-of-plane waves or wrinkles (b) folding (c) in-plane waviness and (d) tearing

Fig. 2. Fabric unit cell

Fig. 3. A single ply of unidirectional prepreg NCF mounted in shear frame (a) before and (b) after deformation

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the in-plane shear behavior for a ply of unidirectional prepreg NCF at the handling temperature

Fig. 5. Shear-frame test configuration highlighting slits in 'arms' of test specimen

Fig. 6. Comparison of the in-plane shear behavior for single-ply samples of a unidirectional NCF at room and processing temperatures

Fig. 7. Four-ply formed hemisphere of $(0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$ pre-preg NCF
 (a) experimental displacement and
 (b) finite element result showing displacement

Fig. 8. Double-dome finite element model with segmented straight binders to accommodate embedded cable

Fig. 9. Forming simulation results without pocket/gap defects underneath the location of the binders

Fig. 10. Cross sectional view of formed double-dome part with pocket/gap defects around cable

Fig.11. Finite element result showing displacement of formed part of $0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ NCF with embedded cable